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4 **Facial reconstruction in the context of**
5 **interdisciplinary archaeological**
6 **research in Banat (Romania)**

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18 **ABSTRACT**

19 Facial reconstruction is a scientific concern with interdisciplinary approaches: medicine, forensics,
20 archeology, etc.; with the support of technology, mechatronics applications and computer programs. In
21 our study, the impact of facial reconstruction in the archeology of the Banat region (Romania) could be
22 of importance because it can help to identify and clarify the diversity of populations that passed through
23 this area over the centuries. The method is little used in Romanian archaeology, although our region
24 has many discoveries and artifacts whose processing and analysis with the help of specific methods and
25 techniques could provide a more precise placement in the historical context.

26 Banat is a "contact" region of Romania characterized by the diversity of the population, resulting
27 from an intense migration flow of various groups over time, from the native populations to those who
28 came from Northern Europe or Central Asia, with very different physiognomy and anatomical
29 characteristics, and reconstructing them could make it easier to understand the past. Our approach is
30 scientific and technical in nature, to understand and gain a better perspective on the cultural baggage of
31 this region, considered even today an example of intercultural coexistence.

32 Our study is based on data and material collected by archaeologists from the West University of
33 Timisoara and the National History Museum of Banat, within an agreement to share materials and
34 knowledge. In perspective, we want to create a database of the human remains discovered by
35 archaeologists on the territory of Banat, through 3D scanning, in an inter-institutional collaboration
36 (between archaeologists, engineers, doctors), which will allow specialists to analyze the remains and
37 clarify the physiognomy of the individuals using techniques in facial reconstruction and 3D computer
38 modeling. The method allows us to collect data and establish biometric indicators: dimensions of the
39 skull, bone tissue, for the individuals found in our excavations, useful to the archaeologist for the
40 reconstruction of the soft tissues of the face, but also for the management and administration of all this
41 data by storing it in a digital archive with a unique code for each object.

42
43 **Keywords:** SDG17, dialogue between technologists and humanists, facial reconstruction –
44 alternative methods (with application in archaeology)

45

Introduction

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47 Trigger warning: Please be advised that this paper discusses topics such as death, maiming
48 and human remains. Reader discretion is advised.

49 Facial reconstruction is a scientific concern with interdisciplinary approaches: medicine,
50 forensics, archeology, etc.; with the support of technology, mechatronics applications and
51 computer programs. In our study, the impact of facial reconstruction in the archeology of the Banat
52 region (located in western Romania) could be of importance because it can help to identify and
53 clarify the diversity of populations that passed through this area over the centuries.

54 The method is little used in Romanian archaeology, although our region has many discoveries
55 and artifacts whose processing and analysis with the help of specific methods and techniques
56 could provide a more precise placement in the historical context.

57 The region of Banat is an ideal location for such an endeavor because of its rich background
58 in terms of population diversity as a result of centuries of intense migration flows or even planned
59 settlements. This facilitated archaeological records of human remains with a wide variety of
60 physiognomies which spills over into the diversity of the present day population. Our hope is to
61 better understand these differences and the story they might tell by analyzing the old remains and
62 comparing them to the present peoples.

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Facial reconstruction in Banat

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66 Localisation

67 Banat region, situated at the west extremity of Romania, presents many and some of the most
68 spectacular archaeological sites in the country. Their diversity is remarkable: Circular or square
69 fortifications, Linear fortifications, Antique and medieval roads, Open settlements, Tumular
70 mounds, etc.

71 Maps reflecting population mobility from the third century to the Middle Ages.

72 The geo-strategic characteristic of the current territory of Romania as a transit zone between
73 East and West, North and South can be observed.

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75 **Figure 1** - Necropolises and funerary discoveries from the historical Banat, X-XIV centuries

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77 The situation illustrated by the map reflects the state of funerary discoveries, which is not very
78 rich, archaeologists focusing more on the research of settlements (villages) and fortifications.

79

80 *Attempt at facial reconstruction in 1960-1982*

81 Graphic reconstructions of some skulls discovered in the archaeological excavations at Dridu
82 (Ialomița county) in a site dating back to the 12th century, conducted at the Institute of Forensic
83 Medicine Mina-Minovici (Bucharest) by Dr. Cantemir Rîșcutia and Irina Rîșcutia.

84 These images in Figures 2.1 and 2.2, and more like them were found in the archives of the
85 Banat Museum during our documentation. It represents an interesting attempt at facial
86 reconstruction undergone with nothing but pen and paper.

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Figure 2.1 - Drown over skull

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Figure 2.2 - Resulted reconstruction

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93 *Methodology. Data acquisition.*

94 Generally speaking, there are five widely accepted methods for developing digital 3D surface
95 models:

96 Photogrammetry

97 The basic principle of generating a 3D model by using photogrammetry, is to photograph the
98 subject from different positions, this way we can obtain a full 3D view. Align and merge multiple
99 2D photographs into a 3D model for analysis. 3D models can be more accurate than anticipated

100 (and technology keeps getting better and better). Multiple consequent photos taken around the
101 object (360 degrees) at different levels (3 or 4).

102 3D surface scanning: laser & structured-light

103 The process of digitizing a physical object into three-dimensional space. The resulting file
104 contains a digital blueprint with geometric coordinate positions. The resulting digital copy is useful
105 for engineering capabilities like reverse engineering and inspection for dimensional analysis but
106 also for analysis, study and manipulation of artifacts.

107 Micro-CT scanning (+ internal bone structures)

108 A diagnostic imaging procedure that uses a combination of X-rays and computer technology to
109 produce images of the inside of the body. It shows detailed images of any part of the body,
110 including the bones, muscles, fat, organs and blood vessels.

111 Microscribe

112 Manual 3D landmark digitizing: imputing raw coordinates one by one via a pen-like appendix
113 resulting in the size and shape (form) of the object being generated with specialized software. It's
114 probably the most hands-on process out of all.

115 Confocal microscope (3D micromorphometry)

116 The primary functions of a confocal microscope are to produce a point source of light and reject
117 out-of-focus light, which provides the ability to image deep into tissues with high resolution, and
118 optical sectioning for 3D reconstructions of imaged samples.

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Materials and methods

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122 Our research unfolded across several stages. Initially, we started with fundamental data
123 acquisition techniques, such as photogrammetry and 3D laser scanning. In the future we plan to
124 further explore more intricate methodologies, including those necessitating collaborative protocols
125 with multiple medical institutions, such as CT scanning and the utilization of a microscribe device.

126 For our first test subject, we decided to choose a skull belonging to an adult male, age 30-40
127 years old, with no discernable pathologies at the skull level. The subject was discovered during
128 the archaeological excavations conducted on the Cistercian abbey from Igris, Romania, and it can
129 be dated between the last half of the 12th century and the first half of the 13th century.

130 We opted to employ the same subject across all our methodologies to ensure a more precise
131 and consistent outcome.

132 In this initial phase of data acquisition, we chose to evaluate two available methods:
133 photogrammetry and 3D surface scanning. We believe these options are among the simplest to
134 grasp, and the associated equipment is both cost-effective and efficient in terms of workflow.

135

136 *Photogrammetry*

137 The basic principle of generating a 3D model by using photogrammetry, is to photograph the
138 subject from different positions, this way we can obtain a full 3D view.

139 Align and merge multiple 2D photographs into a 3D model for analysis.

140 3D models can be more accurate than anticipated (and technology keeps getting better and better)

141 Multiple consequent photos taken around the object (360 degrees) at different levels (3 or 4).

142 From a data acquisition point of view, we opted for two methods. First, the skull was set on a
143 Smart Turntable, with the light source emerging from underneath the turntable, and a black
144 background was used. The camera was set on a tripod, facing the subject and the pictures were
145 taken every two seconds, from three different heights. After the initial pictures were taken, the skull
146 was placed on its back and the process repeated, this was done in order to also capture the bottom
147 of the skull, as well as the interior of the jaw section.

148 Another important factor is the usage of a system of fixed lenses, 50mm, widely used in taking
149 portraits, this being extremely useful in capturing photogrammetry data because the focal point of
150 the picture will always be the subject, in our case the skull.

151 This is what we would consider the standard method of data acquisition, as it offers a constant
152 source of light, the position of the camera is stable and steady and the subject can be captured
153 from all possible angles with ease.

154 In order to better understand the way the images should be captured, as well as the degree of
155 overlap needed to produce the best result, we also opted to place the skull on a rigid support and
156 to move around it while snapping pictures at every step. This was also done from three different
157 heights, to obtain as much data as possible.

158 Also, we used a pair of fixed macro lenses, 105 mm, with vibration assist, to ensure the full blur
159 of the background, as well as the possibility of capturing all the details while also moving.

160 The processing of the raw data was done in Agisoft Metashape, while using the High setting
161 for both the photo alignment process, as well for the point cloud generation process.

162 The 3D model was also done on High parameters, and the texture were added using the Difuse
163 map option, the images themselves providing the data for the textures.

164 The high setting was used to generate 3D models that were easy to work with, from a storage point
165 of view, yet for our final data acquisition process, we will use only the highest possible settings.

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167 **Figure 3** - Model resulted through photogrammetry

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169 *3D surface scanning*

170 This particular method, in comparison with the latter one described, has a very particular and
171 different type of characteristics, and we can name a few: very fast scanning time, it does not require
172 a tripod, very small and light-weight (high transferability), lower resolution and it can be used with
173 the help of some smartphones.

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175 *Anatomy of a 3D model:*

176 When 3D scanning, a vertex is the name of a single point of point obtained through scanning
177 (smallest unit). The line connecting two vertices is called an edge. Three edges form a triangle;

178 this is the smallest generated surface. Finally, we have polygons and faces, these are flat surfaces
179 defined by edges and triangles.

180 *Resolution and Accuracy:*

181 Resolution is the smallest distinguishable unit (piece of surface) in a measured value. A
182 reconstructed 3D surface geometry is made out of linked triangles (Among vertices). The larger
183 and/or fewer triangles there are the less detailed the surface will be. Adversely, the smaller and
184 more numerous the triangles, we have more detail, higher resolution, accuracy, and
185 representation.

186 The use of filters on 3D surfaces, known as surface analysis, is done through image filtering
187 and the transformation of an image's characteristics (size, shape, color, brightness) using semi-
188 automated graphical techniques. Then 3D filter Post-processing (e.g., with Meshlab, Gom Inspect
189 software) is used to "clean" the 3D models, repairing / modifying surfaces (e.g., "smoothing",
190 "closing holes") and reconstructing missing surfaces.

191 For this second data acquisition method, we used a EinScan SE Handheld 3D Scanner, with
192 the subject of our analysis, the skull, placed on the same smart turntable used beforehand.

193 The smart turntable offered us a much needed source of constant light from its own LED's
194 system, as the 3D scanner is not capable to generate its own light source.

195 The entire process was repeat once more by using an iPhone 14 Pro Max, in order to test the
196 potential of the Lidar sensor mounted on this device, and to check for future possible applications
197 of this scanning method.

198 After the raw data was acquired, the points were exported in a ply. format and processed in the
199 open-source software, CloudCompare, with the Faro and Python plug in activated.

200 The setting used in generating the final 3D model varied from medium to high quality, in order
201 to produce a model that was not cumbersome from a storage point of view. Again, as in the case
202 of the latter method, when we will acquire the final raw data, we will process them only on high
203 and highest settings.

204 The model was further post-processed in MeshLab 3D, to remove the turntable, adjust the light
205 and correct certain errors, as well as to edit certain faces and vertexes.

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Figure 4 - Model resulted through 3D surface scanning

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Discussion

The two generated 3D models, photogrammetry and 3D scanning, were further post-processed in MeshLab 3D, to better clean, repair, smooth the vertices, faces and surface, and also to adjust the different light settings.

Our first model, the photogrammetry generated one, had a total of 13,259,336 dense cloud points, and the final 3D model had no less than 371,538 faces.

On the other hand, the 3D scanned model, had 25,338,854 cloud points and a total of 10,505,442 faces in the case of the final product.

Agisoft and CloudCompare both offer a vast array of export formats for their generated 3D models, in our case we chose to opt for the most common three, OBJ Wavefront, 3Rds and STL. Further along the way we will decide which format works best when working in Blender3D or Zbrush.

Both methods have their up's and down's and each method is suited for a certain approach and context, as we will further discuss in the next slide.

Problems encountered:

The ethics of displaying and reconstructing human remains is a thorny subject that has not been very fleshed out in Romanian archeological discourse in the form of guidelines. We believe that this type of work must entail both an appropriate level of respect and dignity for the deceased while not compromising in any way on the research and expositional value of the paper or of the resulted reconstructions. In the case of our work, the amalgamation of factors, such as the period from which the remains hail (medieval), the unknown religious or ethnic origin or even identity of the individual coupled with the rescue excavation origin of the remains, consist in our view an unproblematic ethical base for our research material.

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Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

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